

2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructures (CoRDI)

Proposed Session: RDM Infrastructures

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TiM 2025: An Incubator for FAIR Image Data Management

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Abstract

Biannually, German BioImaging e.V. (GerBI-GMB) organizes the GerBI-GMB Spring School "Trends in Microscopy" (TiM), an intensive microscopy training camp featuring hands-on workshops on various microscopy techniques, sample preparation, optics fundamentals, image analysis, and image data management.

In 2023, TiM introduced an innovative, on-premise research data management (RDM) for image data, a concept that proved highly successful. Building on this momentum, the 2025 edition further expands its RDM initiatives. In collaboration with the DFG-funded project I3D:bio and the data steward team of the NFDI consortium NFDI4BIOIMAGE, TiM provides a unique environment for testing the complete workflow of image data management with a diverse group of users. During the meeting, an OMERO¹-based framework installed on physical hardware donated for the conference facilitates FAIR data management of all acquired and processed image data. Data stewards support participants in uploading and annotating image data according to the REMBI² metadata guidelines. Conference attendees and workshop providers are invited to contribute to a collaborative on-site test case, applying FAIR data management principles across different imaging modalities and image analysis approaches. Feedback from participants is actively gathered to refine and improve RDM strategies. We will introduce our portable data infrastructure framework and present the expanded RDM concept of TiM 2025, report on key results and statistics—including the volume of uploaded image data and its degree of FAIRness—and highlight the valuable feedback from TiM participants.

Keywords: Bioimaging, Microscopy, Data Management, Workshop

Resources

- <https://omero-tim.gerbi-gmb.de>

Author contributions

Author	Contribution according to the CreDIT guidelines
Tom Boissonnet	Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation
Mohsen Ahmadi	Data curation, Investigation
Janina Hanne	Project administration
Ksenia Krooß	Data curation, Investigation
Josh Moore	Supervision, Software
Olaf Selchow	Conceptualization, Resources
Christian Schmidt	Project administration
Jens Wendt	Data curation, Investigation
Cornelia Wetzker	Data curation, Investigation
Stefanie Weidtkamp-Peters	Conceptualization, Supervision

Competing interests

J.M. owns equity in Glencoe Software, Inc, which is a company that sells OMERO-based data management software and services. All other authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

1. Allan, C., Burel, JM., Moore, J. *et al.* OMERO: flexible, model-driven data management for experimental biology. *Nat Methods* **9**, 245–253 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1896>
2. Sarkans, U., Chiu, W., Collinson, L. *et al.* REMBI: Recommended Metadata for Biological Images—enabling reuse of microscopy data in biology. *Nat Methods* **18**, 1418–1422 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01166-8>